

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE ORIGINAL GEORGIAN-ABKHAZ CONFLICT IN ABKHAZIA (JULY 1989) AS DOCUMENTED BY BRITISH PRESS SOURCES

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Introduction:

In the USSR, following the initiation of the so-called "transformation" policy, the Soviet government employed a strategy of turning autonomies against each other to maintain Moscow's influence over the allied republics. This was done both by recognising them as subjects of the USSR and under the pretext of caring for small nations, regardless of whether there was a genuine basis for this in any given autonomy (Cornell 2001: 138). During this period, Abkhazian and Ossetian separatist movements became active in Georgia, namely "Aidgilara" and "Adamon Nikhas," both of which received support from Moscow.

At the end of the Cold War, as the collapse of the Soviet Union became a realistic prospect, Western interest in the political processes within the state increased. The British press, known for its diversity and broad audience reach, represented various ideological platforms and actively reported on the unfolding situation in Georgia and all significant events within the country. Several approaches to information dissemination can be identified: a) Reports were often printed from Soviet, Russian-language publications, which frequently presented a biased, anti-Georgian perspective and did not reflect the real situation. For the Soviet government, the press remained one of the main ideological tools.

b) International press offices in Moscow, which primarily operated in cooperation with the TASS news agency, a principal news outlet for the Soviet government. c) British press correspondents who travelled directly to Georgia to report on the ground. These correspondents were present in Georgia during nearly all critical events, from the tragic incidents of 1989 to other pivotal moments in the recent history of Georgia.

In 2023, our project, "The War of Abkhazia According to the British Press Materials," won a grant for doctoral educational programs (PHDF-23-560) from the Shota Rustaveli Scientific Foundation. This project allows us to delve deeply into Georgian-Abkhazian relations. This article represents one of the paragraphs from the aforementioned materials, focusing on the origins of the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict and the initial armed clashes.

The novelty of this work lies in its coverage of the pivotal events at the end of the 1980s in Georgian history, based on British materials that are being introduced into scientific circulation for the first time. To study the current and problematic issues of Georgia's recent history, a diverse source base is utilised. This includes materials from the Georgian and foreign press, memories of contemporaries, prepared conclusions of

international organisations, archival materials, monographs, and more. For this research, primary sources, represented by press materials, were invaluable. These were sourced from the British press archive "The British Newspaper Archive," one of the largest closed digital bases of the British press. Our work draws on a range of British publications, including "Aberdeen Evening Express," "Aberdeen Press and Journal," "Dundee Courier," "Irish Independent," "Liverpool Echo," "Newcastle Journal," "Reading Evening Post," "Sunday Tribune," "The Courier and Advertiser," "The Scotsman," and others.

In Georgian historiography, there is currently no comprehensive work—whether in the form of an article or a monograph—that discusses the Georgian-Abkhaz conflict using British press materials with diverse and differing viewpoints. An exception to this is the work of American-born journalist Thomas Goltz, "Georgia: Chronicle of War and Political Chaos in the Post-Soviet Caucasus." Goltz arrived in Georgia after the military coup in January 1992 as a correspondent for the "Sunday Times" and also covered the war in Abkhazia.

Methods:

In the process of working on this paper, we employed appropriate research methodologies. Given that the primary task is the study and analysis of press materials related to recent historical events, we employed the retrospective method. This approach allowed us to evaluate and analyse historical events based on their outcomes. To study historical events within the dynamics of time, we applied the principle of historicism, which enables us to observe the development of historical events from their inception and understand their relationship with other processes.

Outcomes:

The article examines the principal aspects of the initial Georgian-Abkhazian armed conflict. It discusses materials from the British press, identifying key trends through a comparative analysis with Georgian press and scholarly literature. We explored the positions of the opposing parties and the significance of the conflict, including its economic and political consequences. The study also addresses the roles played by the Abkhazian separatist movement, the Soviet government, the leadership of the Georgian SSR, and the leaders of the national movement in the unfolding of the conflict.

Based on the study of the materials, we conclude that the British public was informed about the developments on a daily basis and exhibited a high level of interest in the issue.

News was printed in both central and regional publications. The British press mainly discussed the issue in two contexts: 1) as a parallel development of the

"transformation" policy and its relationship with the central government, and 2) as a regional ethnic conflict. The British press's interest in the USSR and the republics seeking separation, including Georgia, did not wane, as evidenced by the numerous publications that appeared in subsequent periods.

The State University of Abkhazia in Sukhumi was a key base for the Abkhazian separatist movement. The situation deteriorated after Aleko Gvaramia was elected as rector. On the 70th anniversary of the opening of the first Georgian university in 1988, Gvaramia addressed the audience in Russian (Papaskiri, 2007, p. 222), which sparked significant protest from the Georgian community. On March 18, 1989, separatist professors and teachers at the State University of Abkhazia signed "Likhni's Appeal." This appeal led to widespread protests across Georgia, culminating in the brutal suppression of peaceful demonstrators on April 9, 1989, in Tbilisi. After the death of Zurab Anchabadze, the university's first rector, separatist forces sought to take control, which began with the appointment of Zaur Avidzba as rector. The separatist faction at the university was led by vice-rector, Professor Oleg Domenia: "It was around this 'national leader' that separatist-minded professors and students rallied" (Papaskiri, 2007, p. 220). Following the anti-Georgian actions of "Aidgilara" in Sukhumi, the issue of establishing a Georgian university became a pressing concern (Papaskiri, 2007, p. 222-225; Jojua, 2009, p. 115-120).

Finally, after pressure from Georgian professors and teachers at Abkhazia State University, as well as from students and Georgian society, the central government of Georgia agreed to open a branch of Tbilisi State University in Sukhumi (Communist, 1989, p. 1). Renowned scientist Professor Felix Tkebuchava was appointed as rector. This decision sparked serious protests from the Abkhazian side. The situation in Sukhumi worsened, peaking on July 15, 1989, when entrance exams were supposed to take place. Leaders of "Aidgilara" received instructions to disrupt the exams, gathered several thousand armed activists in Sukhumi, and on July 15-16 orchestrated a mass attack on Georgians, starting with an assault on the exam centre at Sukhumi's N1 school. Their actions led to a temporary halt in the publication of the Georgian-language newspaper "Soviet Abkhazia" for a week (Soviet Abkhazia, 1989, p. 3). Over the next two weeks, intense clashes erupted between Abkhazians and Georgians in Abkhazia. Georgians from across the country, particularly from the Samegrelo region, came to support their compatriots in Abkhazia. The conflict ceased following the intervention of Soviet internal troops and the involvement of leaders from the Georgian national movement. To resolve the situation, the Presidium of the Supreme Council of the Abkhazian SSR and the Council of Ministers issued a resolution (Kolbaya, Chakhrakia, Gelantia, Latsuzbaya, 2000, p. 52).

The Union of Journalists of Georgia established a press centre in Sukhumi (Communist,

1989, p. 4) with the aim of providing objective information to the public as well as to Soviet and international media. The British press frequently reported on the conflict in Sukhumi, drawing from both Soviet and

Sakinform materials. Starting from July 17, 1989, British publications began featuring reports and detailed articles on the situation in Sukhumi, often placing it against the backdrop of miners' strikes in the USSR, particularly in Ukraine and Siberia. Coverage of the events in Sukhumi continued both in July and the subsequent months.

The first publication on this issue appeared in the Scottish newspaper "The Scotsman" under the title "11 die in Black Sea violence" (The Scotsman, 1989, p. 6). The article provides a detailed account of the events in Sukhumi, stating: "According to the latest reports, 11 people have already died in the conflict that erupted in Sukhumi, the centre of Abkhazia on the Black Sea coast" (The Scotsman, 1989, p. 6). The article also cites information from the Soviet news agency TASS regarding the planned deployment of troops to restore order in Abkhazia. The report mentions that "Georgians and Abkhazians confronted each other with batons, knives, and firearms" (The Scotsman, 1989, p. 6).

The second report appeared in "Birmingham Mail" under the title "Georgian ethnic unrest" (Birmingham Mail, 1989, p. 2). This edition includes a telephone interview with Said Tarkili, a high-ranking official of the Abkhazian SSR, who claimed that "the confrontation was initiated by the Georgian side, which aimed to separate the State University of Abkhazia and merge it with the new educational institution established by Tbilisi State University, thereby restricting the admission of Abkhazians" (Birmingham Mail, 1989, p. 2). Tarkili further stated: "The Abkhaz side opposes this because dividing the university by nationality is unacceptable" (Birmingham Mail, 1989, p. 2). The article provides a detailed account of events in Abkhazia since March of that year, noting that the situation deteriorated after Abkhazians expressed their desire to leave Georgia, leading to protests, the suppression of peaceful demonstrators in

Tbilisi, and resulting casualties. The report also highlights that Abkhazia has a population of 535,000, including 91,000 Abkhaz, and holds the status of an autonomous republic" (Birmingham Mail, 1989, p. 2). Notably, Said Tarkili personally attended a meeting of Abkhazian separatists on July 8 of the same year, held at the Union of Abkhazian Writers, where attendees demanded that exams for the Sukhumi branch of Tbilisi University be cancelled: "Several extremists directly threatened, saying, 'Otherwise, we will organise a "second Ferghana" for you'" (Communist, 1989, p. 4).

On July 20, the Irish newspaper "Irish Independent" published a report titled "11 killed in Soviet riots" (Irish Independent, 1989, p. 22), stating: "11 people have already died in severe clashes and 128 have been hospitalised" (Irish Independent, 1989, p. 22).

Among the publications printed in the following days, the article in the Cambridge Daily News titled "Rioting leaves 14 dead" (Cambridge Daily News, 1989, p. 4) stands out. It discusses the complicated situation in Sukhumi and Abkhazia in general, including the seizure of firearms by opposing parties. The article states: "In various cities of Western Georgia, citizens broke into prisons and police buildings, opened fire on state institutions" (Cambridge Daily News, 1989, p. 4). The author refers to the city of Zugdidi, from which

prisoners escaped, and the attacks on state bodies in other cities, during which: "the attackers seized hunting rifles confiscated from the population, as well as weapons belonging to the internal affairs bodies" (Kommunisti, 1989, p. 1). The same article, based on information provided by the representative of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Georgia, Gizo Grdzeldze, notes that "400 Georgians and Abkhazians took part in just one skirmish near the Gumi River" (Cambridge Daily News, 1989, p. 4). As a result of the confrontation, several participants were injured. On the same day, July 16, a clash took place near the Ghalidzga River in the Ochamchire district, in which three Georgians were killed (Kommunisti, 1989, p. 1). "Leaders of the Georgian National Movement, especially Merab Kostava, as well as the political leadership of Georgia played a big role in stopping the conflicting parties. The intervention of Colonel-General of Internal Troops Yuriy Shatilin was also important" (Papaskiri, 2010, p. 338). According to the same newspaper report, the people of Abkhazia wrecked railway tracks in certain areas, disrupting train services. The publication includes information from an interview with Vadim Bakatin, Minister of Internal Affairs of the USSR, who mentioned that plans were in place to deploy up to 3,000 militiamen and soldiers from other regions of Georgia to Abkhazia, with internal troops being sent in from Moscow (Cambridge Daily News, 1989, p. 4). The same article notes that three senior officials arrived in Sukhumi from Tbilisi to manage the situation: Givi Gumbaridze, Secretary of the Central Committee of the Georgian SSR; Otar Cherkezia, Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Georgian SSR; and Otar Chitanava, Secretary of the Zugdidi District Committee of the Georgian Communist Party.

According to the newspaper "Dundee Courier," "on the Black Sea coast, in the resort town of Sukhumi, Soviet troops, intended to act as a buffer between Georgians and Abkhazians, have already begun to restore order" (Dundee Courier, 1989, p. 7).

The article published in the "Cambridge Daily News" under the title "Strikes are threatening Perestroika - Gorbachev" (Cambridge Daily News, 1989, p. 4) is significant for understanding the broader Soviet context of the conflict in Abkhazia. It discusses the developments in Abkhazia against the backdrop of the ongoing miners' strikes in the Soviet Union. The publication notes that "the controversy associated with strikes in Abkhazia may threaten Gorbachev's economic and political reforms" (Cambridge Daily News, 1989, p. 4). Abkhazia was an important resort area of the USSR, and the current controversy also impacted the tourist season. This issue was covered in the Manchester Evening News, which published an article titled "Thousands of tourists flee" (Manchester Evening News, 1989, p. 4), informing readers that "thousands of tourists are leaving the Black Sea coast as armed citizens and gangs are rife, and industrial facilities in the region have also been shut down" (Manchester Evening News, 1989, p. 4). According to the same report, the local authorities have banned both Soviet and foreign tourists from entering the region for their own safety.

According to the newspaper "Irish Independent," during the Georgian-Abkhaz conflict in Abkhazia:

"During the riots in Abkhazia, they attacked the dam of the hydroelectric station (meaning Enguri Dam) and tried to disrupt its work" (Irish Independent, 1989, p. 22). Due to the dire situation in Sukhumi, a group of citizens protested: "Enguri Dam workers were forced to start releasing water from the reservoir and practically stop the operation of the power plant" (Communist, 1989, p. 4). The same publication included reports from "Заря Востока" about the wounded in the Ochamchire district, Jvari, and Merkula. In the next issue of "Irish Independent," considerable space is again devoted to the developments in the USSR. Against the backdrop of the agreement reached by the Soviet authorities with the Kuzbas and Siberian miners, it is noted that the situation in Georgia remains difficult, highlighting the significant role of the "Engurhesi" hydroelectric plant and the losses caused by its shutdown (Irish Independent, 1989, p. 26).

The letter published by the British Caucasian and Abkhazologist Brian George Hewitt on July 21, 1989, in the newspaper "Literary Georgia" is significant: "A Foreigner's Observation of the Tense Relationship Between Abkhazians and Georgians (An Open Letter to Georgians)" (Literary Georgia, 1989, pp. 2-3). This letter, dated from May of the same year, appears to attempt to take a conciliatory stance between the Georgians and the Abkhazians. However, it is laden with accusations against the Georgian people, claiming they oppressed the Abkhazians and attempted to assimilate them. Among other grievances, Hewitt urges Georgians to apologise to the Abkhazians for decisions made during Stalin and Beria's time, including the reforms that impacted the Abkhazian language: "Let Georgians understand the sad history of Western Georgia of this century, admit their guilt, and apologise to the Abkhazians" (Literary Georgia, 1989, pp. 2-3). This appeal elicited response letters from Georgian society. It should be noted that Brian George Hewitt actively lobbies for the Abkhazian side and continues to blame the Georgians.

During the effort to restore order, many Georgian law enforcement officers sustained serious injuries. A Georgian militiaman, Ramin Chochia, was killed with a hunting rifle in the village of Primorskoe, Gudauti region (Communist, 1989, p. 1). The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the USSR, which was sent to manage the situation in Abkhazia, faced resistance during their efforts to confiscate weapons. Notably, two soldiers were killed by Abkhazians in the village of Otapi, Ochamchiri district, on July 21, 1989 (Soviet Abkhazia, 1989, p. 3). This incident was reported in the "Lincolnshire Echo": "Locals armed with hunting rifles in Abkhazia killed two members of the internal troops. Clashes between Georgians and Abkhazians continue" (Lincolnshire Echo, 1989, p. 26).

Due to the tragedy in Abkhazia, the authorities of the Georgian SSR declared July 25, 1989, a day of mourning (Communist, 1989, p. 1). The subsequent investigation led to the punishment of only a few ordinary supporters and officials of "Aidgilara," while the main instigators of the conflict remained unpunished. Fourteen people died in the clashes—nine Georgians and five Abkhazians—with several hundred more injured. Among the deceased was one Vladimir (Vova) Vekua,

a prominent leader of the national movement in Abkhazia, who was killed with extreme brutality.

By the end of July 1989, the wave of protest from Georgian society had moved to Tbilisi. The ongoing demonstrations in the capital were extensively covered by the British press.

The article by renowned British political columnist Peter Conrad, titled 'Georgia Goes Against Moscow' (Liverpool Daily [Welsh Edition], 1989, p. 10), provides an in-depth account of the ongoing rally in Tbilisi. The piece notes that 'at least 20,000 Georgians took to the streets, waving flags and chanting "Long live free Georgia! Down with the Russian Empire!"' (Liverpool Daily [Welsh Edition], 1989, p. 10). Conrad highlights that this march is the largest since the brutal suppression of peaceful protesters on April 9. The article describes the procession's route: 'In front of the Government House, where the protesters had assembled (April 9), the crowd paused to pay their respects with raised hands and a minute's silence' (Liverpool Daily [Welsh Edition], 1989, p. 10). The demonstrators then proceeded along Rustaveli Avenue to the Academy of Sciences building. There, speakers voiced their opposition to the Abkhazian separatists, leading 30 students to initiate a sit-in, with three of them declaring a hunger strike. The publication also revisits the tragic events of April 9, 1989, and the suffering of the Georgian people.

In the July 31 issue of the Irish Independent, a photo was published with the caption: 'Seized weapons... Soviet soldiers display hundreds of firearms confiscated from Georgia during the ethnic clashes in the Abkhaz region two weeks ago' (Irish Independent, 1989, p. 9).

In the December issue of The Kilmarnock Standard, a notice was published titled 'Council Refuses' (The Kilmarnock Standard, 1989, p. 15). It reported that the town council received a letter from Abkhazia, whose central city, Sukhum, is twinned with Kilmarnock. The letter addressed the confrontation that took place in July of the same year. However, the mayor, Richard Jenner, decided: 'This is a very difficult situation, and we must not meddle in it' (The Kilmarnock Standard, 1989, p. 15).

Conclusion:

In final analysis, the Georgian-Abkhaz conflict of July 1989 garnered extensive coverage from the British press, reflecting significant interest in the issue. Both small reports and analytical articles appeared daily, highlighting the high level of engagement with the conflict. A pivotal moment in this conflict was the "Likhni Address" of March 18, 1989, which intensified tensions between Georgians and Abkhazians. Georgian society perceived a tangible threat of losing Abkhazia and its potential separation, which led to a surge in political activism.

This activism met with violent resistance from the separatist organisation "Aidgilara," which, supported by the Soviet government, aimed to remove Georgians from positions of authority, despite their larger demographic presence in the region. "Aidgilara" had a clear objective of merging Abkhazia directly with the RSFSR.

British publications not only reported on the unfolding events but also engaged in analysis within the context of Soviet transformation politics and ethnic conflicts. These publications provided valuable insights into the positions of both parties involved, exploring the political and economic dimensions of the situation. They highlighted the unique status of the Abkhazian SSR as an autonomous republic within Soviet Georgia, a status that seemed disproportionate given the Abkhazian population's size relative to Georgians.

The comparison of British press coverage with that of Georgian newspapers like

Communist, Soviet Abkhazia, and Literary Georgia allows for a detailed reconstruction of the conflict's progression. This comparison reveals the escalation from initial clashes to a full-scale military confrontation. The involvement of external forces, initially the Soviet government and later the Russian Federation, played a crucial role in escalating the conflict.

A significant aspect of the British coverage was the letter by Brian George Hewitt, a British scholar, published in Literary Georgia on July 21, 1989. In this letter, Hewitt attempted to mediate between Georgians and Abkhazians but also levelled accusations against the Georgian people for historical oppression of Abkhazians. His call for Georgians to apologise and acknowledge their historical wrongs provoked a wide-ranging response within Georgian society.

During the early stages of the conflict, Georgian correspondents established a press centre in Sukhumi, which was instrumental in spreading information. British media highlighted the intense public interest in Georgia and the various efforts to address the conflict. The involvement of key Georgian figures, such as Zviad Gamsakhurdia and Merab Kostava, along with leaders from the national movement and the government, was pivotal in the conflict resolution process.

The protests in Tbilisi, where up to 20,000 Georgians rallied against the separatist movement in Abkhazia and the Soviet government, were extensively covered by British media. These demonstrations, described as the largest since the April 9 events, underscored the anti-Soviet sentiment and the Georgians' demands for independence from the USSR.

Overall, the examination of British press materials provides an external perspective on the Georgian-Abkhaz conflict, offering a broader understanding of the events. This analysis aids in comprehending the conflict's causes, progression, and implications within the larger context of Soviet dissolution, contributing to the global discourse on Soviet transformation and the emergence of the post-Soviet world order.

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